

DELIVERABLE 2.4

**MATRIX OF TYPE AND
COMPOSITION OF FPNS, THEIR
TRANSFORMATIONAL CAPACITY
AND THEIR ENGAGEMENT WITH
DEPRIVED AND VULNERABLE
GROUPS**

AUTHORS

Ferne Edwards, Roberta Sonnino, Marta López Cifuentes and Haley Parzonko

With contributions from

Cardiff University, Humboldt-Universitaet Zu Berlin, Instituto de Ciencias Sociais, Universita di Pisa, Vrije
Universiteit Amsterdam and ICLEI Africa

20 September 2023

Funded
by the European Union

PROJECT ACRONYM:	FoodCLIC
PROJECT NUMBER:	101060717
WORK PACKAGE NUMBER AND TITLE:	WP2: Mapping and gapping
LEAD BENEFICIARY:	University of Surrey
WORK PACKAGE LEADER:	University of Surrey
RELEVANT TASK:	Task 2.2: Analyze FPNs and understand their capacity to initiate and support change in the urban food environment and food system
DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	Public
DUE DATE (MONTH):	M13
VERSION:	Revised version after RP1 review 17.06.2024

Funded by
the European Union

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Background and objectives	5
2. Methodology	6
2.1 The regional reviews	6
2.2 The guidelines	6
2.3 Refining the data	12
2.4 Identifying compositional types of FPNs and FPN diversity	12
3. The Matrix	14
3.1 Exploring the diversity of the compositional types	16
3.2 Exploring the diversity of the matrix	18
4. A focus on vulnerable and marginalised groups and transformational capacity	24
4.1 FPNs' engagement with vulnerable and marginalised groups	24
4.2 The transformational capacity of FPNs	33
5. Conclusions	41
6. references	42

HISTORY OF CHANGE

June 17, 2024

Number	Page	Change
1	29, 30, 31, 38 and 39	12 additional FPNs have been added to be featured in the main text of the report. In total, 24 FPNs are assessed in the report. The main changes to the report include the following: 1) Addition of text boxes that provide the profile (FPN type, aim, background and sources) to each FPN.
2	24-27 34-37	Additional rows of FPN examples have been added to Tables 5 and Table 7
3	19, 23, 28, 30 and 33	Small edits to the body of the text to reference the 24 FPNs featured in the report.

1. BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

Recent years have seen the emergence of novel collaborations between key food system actors, many of whom seek to change policy towards food system transformation. These networks of food system stakeholders – referred to as Food Policy Networks (FPNs) in this report – exist in diverse compositions around the world. For example, in North America, Food Policy Council (FPC) is the most commonly used term, where alternatively other terms include food councils, coalitions, committees, task forces, alliances, partnerships, boards and steering groups (Santo et al., 2020). **To date, no comprehensive review has been conducted of the diversity of their compositional forms, their impact on vulnerable and marginal groups, or their capacity to instigate transformation in the food system.**

This report contributes to Task 2.2 of the EU FoodCLIC project and is led by the University of Surrey. It **reviews literature** on FPNs through an innovative focus on:

1. The composition of diverse types of FPNs,
2. Attention to the mechanisms that have been deployed to enhance participation of representatives from vulnerable and deprived groups; and,
3. Highlights their capacity to initiate and support change in the urban food environment as a leverage point to transform the city-regional food system.

Insights from this task are synthesised into a **matrix with global geographical coverage**, with examples from North America, Asia, Africa, Europe and beyond to showcase the diversity and location of these FPNs. Furthermore, text boxes of detailed FPN examples are provided throughout the report to emphasise their important characteristics, such as their composition, age, scale, location and topic, their focus on vulnerable and marginal groups and their transformational capacity. By synthesising this research into the matrix and the text boxes, this report will form the basis of discussion for knowledge-sharing workshops with the FoodCLIC Living Lab teams (based in Århus, Amsterdam, Barcelona, Berlin, Braşov, Budapest, Capannori and Lisbon) to support the development and scaling-up of empowered FPNs (in WP3). It will also provide a base from which to identify a sample of different types of FPNs for interviews and case studies for subsequent research within this project (as part of Task 2.2).

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 THE REGIONAL REVIEWS

Each partner was assigned a city or region to review. The assigned regions for each partner were:

- The University of Surrey reviewed Austria, Spain, Central and South America, Australia, New Zealand and the Middle East;
- Cardiff University reviewed North America (including Canada) and the United Kingdom;
- Humboldt University reviewed Germany, Switzerland and Asia;
- The University of Lisboa reviewed Portugal and Brazil;
- ICLEI Africa reviewed central and southern Africa;
- The University of Pisa reviewed Mediterranean Europe; and,
- Vrije Universiteit reviewed northern Europe (the Netherlands, Belgium and Scandinavia).¹

2.2 THE GUIDELINES

The guidelines were designed **to coordinate the regional literature review** conducted by the project partners in their native languages (English, Italian, German, Dutch, Spanish and Portuguese), which would allow for comparability across the research results for analysis. Material for the search was divided into two parts: first, the guidelines used to conduct their research, and second, an Excel datasheet template to collect the selected data.

Partners were first asked to choose an academic source/s to search for data (such as Google Scholar or Web of Science). This data could be supplemented by additional data search using policy and grey literature, such as project reports, case studies, handbooks and/or information briefs that relate to FPNs. The inclusion of contextual knowledge from partners' own city-regions was also encouraged. Key search terms were to be translated into **partners' native language within the last 10 years**. The date range of 10 years was a general guide – other articles outside this timeframe could be used if they provided better information and referred to FPNs still in existence. The guidelines prompted reviewers to consider any significant translation issues. For example, to

¹ While attempts were made to search the entire globe for FPNs, regions represented by the partner's considerable language abilities were prioritised, where not all FPNs could be found online in English. For example, FPNs in eastern Europe were lacking. While the LL teams from Hungary and Romania also reviewed FPNs in their respective countries, FPNs in countries beyond these in eastern Europe that were only listed in their native languages may have been overlooked.

ask: Do terms have the same or different connotations in different languages? Are there different cultural preferences for food policy examples in different cities? Are new terms needed to address urban food policy in different cities? If so, what are these and how do they differ? Comments about the review process were captured either as notes or in group meetings.

The study comprised three phases. In the first phase:

- FPNs were defined as a broad network of actors that intersects with policy.
- Diverse types of FPNs were prioritized by using suggested terms such as food policy network; food policy assemblages; urban food policy; urban food strategies; community food system, and more (see category 1 of table 1).
- Other terms could also be used that were more specific to FPNs in each specific region.
- While FPNs could be multi-scalar, their features should relate to urban and/or city-regions.

In the second phase:

- Partners were asked to focus on FPNs’ engagement with vulnerable and deprived groups (i.e., the FoodCLIC aspect of inclusion of citizens in the design, implementation and monitoring of policies). To meet this objective, suggested key terms were listed in category 2 in table 1.

In the third phase:

- Partners were asked to refine the search by exploring FPNs’ transformational capacity (see category 3; to combine search terms from categories 1 and 3).

Table 1: Search categories and suggested key search terms, as expressed in the Guidelines

CATEGORY AND DEFINITION	SUGGESTED KEY SEARCH TERMS IN ENGLISH. <i>PLEASE ADAPT THESE TERMS TO YOUR REGION’S LANGUAGE AND CHARACTERISTICS.</i>
1. ‘Food policy networks’ (FPNs) are defined in the DOA as being “ endorsed by relevant institutions from the quadruple helix – can constitute a broad and inclusive science-policy-practice interface that	Food policy network; food policy assemblages; urban food policy; urban food strategies; community food system; translocal food governance; food policy council; food security policy; urban food policy; local food network; food innovation network; food safety policies; alternative food network; community food network; urban farming policy/network; urban agriculture policy/network; food waste policy/network; community supported agriculture policy/council/network;

<p>generates transformative knowledge, supports the formulation and implementation of integrated urban food policies and empowers food system actors around a shared vision of the urban food system”.</p> <p>For this task, we are interested in city-region and/or urban FPNs.</p>	<p>food + local environment policy/network/council; public procurement policy/network/council; fair trade policy/network/council; food sharing network/council; sustainable food policy/ network/council; environmental food policy/council/network; ecological food policy/council/network; urban food regime.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">AND</p> <p>City; city region; urban (possibly, also: municipal; council; local government).</p>
<p>2. Vulnerable and deprived groups: inclusion of all food system actors and citizens, while ensuring also a fairer distribution of its outcomes.</p>	<p>Vulnerable/deprived groups; migrants; the elderly; school children; food insecure. + participation, inclusion/inclusive, exclusion, equity/equitable, integrated, representation</p>
<p>3. Transformational capacity of FPNs</p>	<p>Food system change; transition; transformation; social change; circular cities; socio-ecological change/transition; system change.</p>

FPN examples from the regional reviews were compiled into one longlist of **more than 100 cases** (see Table 2 below).

Table 2: FPN examples from the regional reviews collated into the “super matrix”

Region	Location	Name of example
Africa	Antananarivo, Madagascar	The Antananarivo Food Policy Council*
	Bungoma and Busia counties, Kenya	Nutrition in City Ecosystems
	Southern Africa	African Food Security Urban Network*
	Nairobi, Kenya	Nairobi and Environs Food Security, Agriculture and Livestock Forum
	Nairobi and Kisumu, Kenya	Food Liaison Advisory Groups*
	Lusaka, Zambia	Lusaka Food Policy Council
	Bambilor, Kaffrine and Kounghoul in Senegal	CIGA (Local initiative committee on food governance)

	Benin, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cameroun, Congo, Ivory Coast, Gambia, Kenya, Mali, Niger, Central African Republic, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Sudan, Togo, Uganda, and Zambia.	African Network on the Right to Food
	Dar es Salaam, Tanzania	Tanzania Food Gardening Network
	Maputo, Mozambique	Associação para Desenvolvimento Sustentável (ABIODES)
	Nairobi and Kisumu, Kenya	Food Liaison Advisory Groups*
	Tanzania	Arusha Food Safety Committee
	Western Cape, South Africa	Western Cape Economic Development Partnership (EDP) - Food Forum
	South Africa (both urban and rural areas)	Southern Africa Food Lab
	Uganda	Mbale City Food Systems Platform
Asia	Bangkok, Thailand	Working Group for Food for Change*
	China	Good Food Academy
	Seoul, South Korea	Seoul Food Citizens Committee*
	Singapore	The Social Enterprise
	Singapore	The Collective
Australia and New Zealand	Australia-wide	Australia's Right to Food Coalition*
	Australia-wide	Sustain: the Australian Food Network
	Brisbane-based, Australia wide	Food Connect Shed
	Merri-bek Council in Melbourne, Australia	Merri-bek Food Leadership Action Group (FLAG)
	7 Local Government Areas in North East Victoria, Australia	North East Local Food Strategy Working Group
	Adelaide, South Australia	SA Urban Food Network
	Illawarra, New South Wales	Food Fairness Illawarra
	Dunedin, New Zealand	Good Food Dunedin (Dunedin) / Good Food Dunedin Alliance
	Northland, New Zealand	Northland Food Policy Council (Northland) / Northland Food Policy Network: He Kai Ora Tonu
Central and South America	Cali, Colombia	The Territorial Council of Food and Nutritional Sovereignty and Security
	Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil	Feira do Pequeno Produtor de Passo Fundo
	Southern Brazil	Ecovida Network
	Cali, Colombia	The Food and Nutritional Security and Sovereignty Roundtable of Cali
	Cali, Colombia	Academic Platform on Food and Nutritional Safety
	Colombia	Red de Semillas Libres de Colombia
	Cuba	Asociación Nacional de Agricultores Pequeños*
	Mesoamerica (Guatemala, Nicaragua, and other countries)	Campesino a Campesino Movement
	Cuba	National Association of Small Farmers (Asociación Nacional de Agricultores Pequeños; ANAP)*
	Quito, Ecuador	Quito Agri-Food Pact (PAQ)

	Ecuador	Colectivo Agroecológico and the Movimiento de Economía Social y Solidaria (MESSE)*
	La Paz, Bolivia	Municipal Committees for Food Security (CMSAs) / Municipal Food Security Committee of La Paz (MFSC-LPZ)
	Chile	ANAMURI - National Association of Rural and Indigenous Women
	Mexico	Mexican Network of Organic Markets (La Red Mexicana de Tianguis y Mercados Organicos)
	Lima, Peru	La Red de Agricultura Ecológica del Perú (RAE-PERÚ)
	Ecuador	Colectivo Agroecológico and the Movimiento de Economía Social y Solidaria*
	Paraguay	Coordinadora Nacional de Organizaciones de Mujeres Trabajadoras Rurales e Indígenas
	Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil	Feira do Pequeno Produtor de Passo Fundo
	Lima, Peru	Healthy Eating Environments Taskforce
	Quito, Ecuador	Quito Agri-Food Pact
Europe	Vienna, Austria	Viennese Food Policy Council (Wiener Ernährungsrat)
	Ghent, Belgium	Gent en Garde*
	Brussels, Belgium	Ceinture Aliment-Terre Liègeoise
	Brussels, Belgium	Le Début des Haricots*
	Bruges, Belgium	Food Lab Brugge
	Brussels, Belgium	GASAP (solidarity purchasing group for peasant agriculture)
	Turin, Italy	RePoPP - Re-design Project of Organic waste in Porta Palazzo market (Progetto Organico Porta Palazzo)
	Rome and Milan, Italy	RECUP
	Finland	Finnish National Nutrition Council (Valtion ravitsemusneuvottelukunta)
	Finland	Finnish Society for Food Education RUUKKU (Ruokakasvatusyhdistys RUUKKU)
	Finland	Finnish Organic Association (Luomuliitto ry)
	Mouans-Sartoux, France	Project alimentare territorial del Maison de l'éducation à l'alimentation durable (MEAD)
	Córdoba, Spain	Mesa de coordinación del Pacto de Milán, Córdoba*
	Madrid, Spain	Milan Pact Follow-up Committee (Mesa de seguimiento del Pacto de Milán de Madrid)
	Valencia, Spain	Valencia Municipal Food Council (Consell Alimentari Municipal de València - CALM)
	Switzerland	Ernährungszukunft Schweiz*
	Zurich, Switzerland (with partners in other Swiss and Austrian regions)	Kompetenznetzwerk Ernährungswirtschaft
	The Netherlands	City Deal Food on the Urban Agenda and Healthy and Sustainable Food Environments
	The Hague, the Netherlands	Ons eten Den Haag*
	The Netherlands	Voedsel Anders
	Provinces of Flevoland and Noord Holland	Voedsel Verbindt
	Amsterdam Metropolitan Area	Food Council MRA
	Municipality of Ede	Eetbaar Ede

	Metropolitan area Rotterdam, The Hague	Food Council Rotterdam
	Wallon Brabant	Made-in-BW
	Birmingham, UK	Birmingham Food Policy Council*
	Brighton & Hove, UK	Brighton & Hove Food Partnership*
	Vienna, Austria	Wiener Ernährungsrat
	Portugal	Alimentar Cidades Sustentáveis
	Lisbon Metropolitan Area, Portugal	FoodLink - Network for the Food Transition in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area
	Zagreb and Istria, Croatia	Solidary Ecological Group*
	Montpellier Méditerranée Métropole, France	P2A - Politique agroécologique et alimentaire de Montpellier
	In Germany: Marburg, Nebelschütz, Berlin, Cologne; France: Mouans-Sartoux, Loos-en-Gohelle	Franco-German Forum for the Future / Deutsch-Französische Zukunftswerk
	Oldenburg, Germany	Food Policy Council Oldenburg
	Berlin, Germany	Berlin Food Policy Council
	Berlin and North-East Germany	LebensMittelPunkt
	20 cities in Germany	Biostädte/Organic cities
Global	Victoria-based in Australia; now operating in 20 countries.	Open Food Network
	Global	La Via Campesina*
	Fort Portal, Uganda Zambia and Indonesia	Food Change Lab*
Middle East	Amman, Jordan	City Strategic Agenda*
	Pan-Arab regional network including 13 Arab countries	Arab Network for Food Sovereignty*
	Lebanon, Palestine	Healthy Kitchens Healthy Children Programme
	Amman, Jordan	Al-Barakah Wheat project*
North America	New York, USA	Syracuse-Onondaga Food Systems Alliance*
	Ottawa, Canada	Ottawa County Food Policy Council*
	Indiana, USA	Evansville Area Food Council
	Denver, USA	Denver Sustainable Food Policy Council
	Illinois, USA	Chicago Food Policy Action Council
	Ohio, USA	Cleveland-Cuyahoga County Food Policy Coalition
	Colorado, USA	El Paso County Food Policy Advisory Board
	Georgia, USA	Savannah Chatham Food Policy Council
	New Hampshire, USA	Greater Nashua Food Council
	Washington, USA	Whatcom Food Network
	Kansas, USA	Food and Farm Council of Riley County and City of Manhattan, Kansas
	Canada	Sustain Ontario's Municipal Food Policy Network*
	Canada	Food Policy Council for Kingston, Frontenac and Lennox-Addington

* These examples are profiled in more detail in the text boxes and tables.

2.3 REFINING THE DATA

To produce a robust, manageable and diverse sample, the collated entries were further refined to **47 examples** (see chapter 3). Exclusion criteria used to arrive at the shortlist were:

- **Not acting at a policy level** – For example, ‘alternative food networks’ do not always act at a policy level.
- **Temporary, funding-driven networks** – For example, networks that were created in response to European Research and Innovation’s calls.
- **FPNs that had no link to the city-regional level** – While many FPNs may be multi-scalar, FPNs that could be related to urban and/or city-regions were prioritised.
- **Being within the city-regions of the Living Labs** – As the matrix sought to offer all partners the opportunity to understand diverse interpretations of FPNs across the globe, FPNs that were part of the FoodCLIC Living Labs were purposefully not included.
- **Limited available data** – Not enough data were available to fill the inclusion criteria above.
- **Not of high priority for the purpose of the Living Labs** – For example, while we strove to illustrate a diversity of locations, FPNs from Europe were prioritised as a region of particular interest for the Living Labs.

2.4 IDENTIFYING COMPOSITIONAL TYPES OF FPNs AND FPN DIVERSITY

Each FPN in the shortlist represents at least one example of each compositional type that meet the inclusion criteria as collated from the regional reviews. To identify compositional types, each FPN example was assigned a three-word descriptor that echoed the exact wording of the FPN title as closely as possible to its title in its native language. It was not always straightforward to determine as three-word descriptors were not always provided, FPNs would sometimes use multiple classifications and/or use classifications without distinction.

Other compositional features we looked at included:

- **The degree of government involvement** – Being “with” or “without” government support explores the extent and type of relationship a FPN has with a local government institution. For example, a FPN “with government” could be directly linked, such as being established by a government to advise them, or indirectly linked, where government may be an active partner in the network. Alternatively, “without government” could mean that the FPN is completely separate from government in terms of placement, allocation of resources or funding, or through membership.

The degree of government involvement can present both benefits and barriers (see Edwards et al., 2023). For example, placing an FPN within a government institution can provide policy legitimacy and support (de Zeeuw and Dubbeling, 2015), while “too much municipal control and excessive project implementation limit a community’s own leadership and opportunity to develop a project based on their own defined goals” (Lake, 2019: 6; also see Sibbing and Candel, 2021). As a result, some FPNs chose to “remain largely autonomous from government control, and, hence, less affected by political parties, electoral cycles and a reliance on government funding schemes” (Edwards et al., 2023: 18). As the degree of government involvement can greatly impact the approach and efficacy of a FPN, we have provided examples in the shortlist for those “with” and “without” in the two most popular examples of FPCs and FPNs.

■ **The type and degree of stakeholder membership of the FPN** – Another feature that impacts the composition of FPNs is their diversity of membership and the extent to which the quadruple helix (government, private sector, civil society and academia) is represented in the FPN. Some FPNs are civil society based, while others have a wider variety of actors and organisations from across the quadruple helix. Which stakeholder initiates the FPN also impacts on their approach, topic and membership.

Besides features that relate directly to compositional type, we also looked at other features of the selected FPNs to get more insight into their diversity. We identified geographical spread, age, topic, goals, trajectories, and size of membership, target group and transformational capacity, as relevant features concerning FPN diversity. We paid specific attention to the latter two features during the second and third phase (see section 1.2.2), because of the focus of the FoodCLIC project on food-deprived and vulnerable groups and the role of FPNs as catalyst for food system transformation.

3. THE MATRIX

This selection process resulted in a shortlist including 47 FPNs. These FPNs classified themselves in many different ways. Apart from the terms FPN and FPC many other terms were used by FPNs to indicate their compositional type. In total 43 FPN compositional types were identified as presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: An overview of FPNs by FPN type, region, location and example

FPN type	Region	Location	Name of example
ADVISORY GROUP	Africa	Nairobi and Kisumu, Kenya	Food Liaison Advisory Groups*
AGENDA	Middle East	Amman, Jordan	City Strategic Agenda*
ALLIANCE	North America	New York, USA	Syracuse-Onondaga Food Systems Alliance*
ASSEMBLY	Europe	Switzerland	Ernährungszukunft Schweiz*
ASSOCIATION	Central and South America	Cuba	Asociación Nacional de Agricultores Pequeños*
CITY DEAL	Europe	The Netherlands	City Deal Food on the Urban Agenda and Healthy and Sustainable Food Environments
COALITION	Australia	Australia-wide	Australia's Right to Food Coalition*
COLLECTIVE	Central and South America	Ecuador	Colectivo Agroecológico and the Movimiento de Economía Social y Solidaria*
COMMITTEE	Asia	Seoul, South Korea	Seoul Food Citizens Committee*
	Europe	Córdoba, Spain	Mesa de coordinación del Pacto de Milán, Córdoba*
CONSORTIUM	Africa	Bungoma and Busia counties, Kenya	Nutrition in City Ecosystems
COORDINATOR	Central and South America	Paraguay	Coordinadora Nacional de Organizaciones de Mujeres Trabajadoras Rurales e Indígenas
COUNCIL	Central and South America	Cali, Colombia	The Territorial Council of Food and Nutritional Sovereignty and Security
ENTERPRISE	Asia	Singapore	The Social Enterprise
FOOD POLICY COUNCIL	Europe	Ghent, Belgium	Gent en Garde*
		Birmingham, UK	Birmingham Food Policy Council*
		Vienna, Austria	Wiener Ernährungsrat
	North America	Ottawa, Canada	Ottawa County Food Policy Council*
		Indiana, USA	Evansville Area Food Council
Africa	Antananarivo, Madagascar	The Antananarivo Food Policy Council*	
FOOD POLICY NETWORK	Europe	France and Germany	Deutsch-Französische Zukunftswerk
		The Hague, the Netherlands	Ons eten Den Haag*

		Brussels, Belgium	Ceinture Aliment-Terre Liègeoise
	North America	Canada	Sustain Ontario's Municipal Food Policy Network*
	Africa	Southern Africa	African Food Security Urban Network*
FORUM	Africa	Nairobi, Kenya	Nairobi and Environs Food Security, Agriculture and Livestock Forum
INDUSTRY INTEREST GROUP	Europe	Zurich, Switzerland (with partners in other Swiss and Austrian regions)	Kompetenznetzwerk Ernährungswirtschaft
LAB	Global	Fort Portal, Uganda Zambia and Indonesia	Food Change Lab*
MOVEMENT	Global	Global	La Via Campesina*
Other NETWORKS			
<i>Alternative food network</i>	Europe	The Netherlands	Voedsel Anders
<i>Alternative agriculture network</i>		Brussels, Belgium	Le Début des Haricots*
<i>Urban food network</i>		Portugal	Alimentar Cidades Sustentáveis
<i>Informal solidarity economy network / CSA network</i>		Zagreb and Istria, Croatia	Solidary Ecological Group*
<i>Seed network</i>	Central and South America	Colombia	Red de Semillas Libres de Colombia
<i>Farmers' network</i>		Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil	Feira do Pequeno Produtor de Passo Fundo
<i>Regional network</i>	Middle East	Pan-Arab regional network including 13 Arab countries	Arab Network for Food Sovereignty*
<i>Foundation-led network</i>	Asia	China	Good Food Academy
<i>"Think and do" network</i>	Australia	Australia-wide	Sustain: the Australian Food Network
<i>Open source network</i>	Global	Based in Australia, now in 20 countries	Open Food Network
PACT	Central and South America	Quito, Ecuador	Quito Agri-Food Pact
PARTNERSHIP	Europe	Brighton & Hove, UK	Brighton & Hove Food Partnership*
PLATFORM	Central and South America	Cali, Colombia	Academic Platform on Food and Nutritional Safety
PROGRAMME	Middle East	Lebanon, Palestine	Healthy Kitchens Healthy Children Programme

PROJECT	Middle East	Amman, Jordan	Al-Barakah Wheat project*
ROUNDTABLE	Central and South America	Cali, Colombia	The Food and Nutritional Security and Sovereignty Roundtable of Cali
SHED	Australia	Brisbane-based, Australia wide	Food Connect Shed
TASKFORCE	Central and South America	Lima, Peru	Healthy Eating Environments Taskforce
WORKING GROUP	Asia	Bangkok, Thailand	Working Group for Food for Change*

* These examples are profiled in more detail in the text boxes and tables.

3.1 EXPLORING THE DIVERSITY OF THE COMPOSITIONAL TYPES

Three key trends were revealed from mapping of the compositional types:

1. **The broad category of ‘other networks’ – representing all examples except FPNs with ‘network’ in the title – was the most popular category.** Significantly, specific networks within this compositional type are widely diverse, ranging from various forms of alternative food networks through to more specific networks, such as farmers’, regional scales or being foundation-led.
2. **The two most popular *specific* collaborations were FPCs and FPNs.** This finding is matched in online literature searches where these two terms dominate.
3. **Finally, another 25 other categories of FPNs represented were “less than 5 examples each”.**

Examples 1 and 2 below provide an example of a FPC and a FPN.

Example 1: Birmingham Food Policy Council, UK

FPN type: FPC without government; represented by various food projects and a panel of experts (relevant research and professional expertise).

Aim: To work towards securing affordable access to safe, tasty, healthy food for this and future generations by collaborating with local and international communities; to enable decision-makers to understand their impact on food security, food safety and the economy at local, national and global levels.

Background: Incorporated as a Community Interest Company in 2014.

Sources: <https://www.birminghamfoodcouncil.org/>

Example 2: Sustain Ontario's Municipal Food Policy Network, Canada

FPN type: FPN with government; brings together planners, community organisers, public health professionals, food producers, distributors and food champions.

Aim: To share ideas and knowledge to develop and influence policies at the municipal or regional level. It pools resources and experiences to distil best practices and develop solutions to include food in municipal policy decisions.

Background: Established in 2008 as a result of a participatory process that concluded with the need for a collaborative policy and advocacy in the region. In 2015, Sustain Ontario became incorporated as a not-for-profit organisation, where they now have the freedom to take action as an independent organisation.

Sources: <https://sustainontario.com/>

Hence, the matrix significantly broadens current understandings of FPNs both in the literature and around the world as predominantly consisting of FPCs and FPNs. It reveals an **unexpectedly broad diversity of multi-stakeholder collaboration around the world**. It should, however, be noted that our exploratory study, based on desk research, did not allow us to cluster the FPNs and create other types than the self-assigned terms.

With respect to the other compositional feature – with or without government – we observed much diversity in the relationship with government. For example, some FPNs were instigated by government, others had government staff, others had temporary or specific government involvement (such as the provision of funding or space), while others again sought to be independent of government involvement altogether. Regarding type and degree of stakeholder membership of the FPN, we found a large diversity both with respect to involvement of actors and organisations from across the quadruple helix (Figure 1) and which stakeholder initiates the FPN (see Figure 2).

3.2 EXPLORING THE DIVERSITY OF THE MATRIX

FPNs are also diverse in their geographical spread (see Table 2 of the “longlist” above), age, topic, goal, trajectories, scale, size of membership, target group transformational capacity. The latter two will be discussed in more detail in chapter 4.

Figure 1. Examples of different FPNs and their membership compositions

Figure 2. Examples of diverse initiators of FPNs

With respect to **age**, the earliest FPN from the review was established in 1961 (the National Association of Small Farmers, Cuba, Example 16), where FPNs have continued to be established into the present day (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: A timeline of examples of FPNs with their year of establishment

Key events or conditions for their initiation include:

- The existence of a supplementary body to guide urban food strategies and actions, such as the Quito Agri-Food Pact, Ecuador;
- In preparation for, or following events, such as the Good Food Academy, China, that emerged from the Good Food Summit;
- Local response to disasters, such as the crisis-led austerity measures (e.g., Solidary Ecological Group, Croatia);
- Efforts to alleviate enduring urban issues, such as food insecurity, economic or health concerns. (E.g., Syracuse-Onondaga Food Systems Alliance, USA);
- The existence of ongoing contributing bodies to international programmes and networks, such as the Milan Steering Committees (E.g., Mesa de Coordinación del Pacto de Milán, Córdoba, Spain);
- Studies by external partners (E.g., the Committee for Green Amman, Jordan).

Generic yet **diverse topics** of FPNs (where many topics are combined in single FPNs) include:

- Food and nutritional security;
- Social and economic viability, including ethical marketing, innovation, research and development and/or fair prices;
- Empowerment, advocating the right to food and/or food sovereignty;
- Efforts to improve health and rights of women;
- Sharing and distilling best practices of the food system with stakeholders and the wider community;
- Forming a united body to express concerns to policy makers and to respond to planning and policy processes;
- Intention to redefine 'good food' in a more holistic way; and,
- The desire to create an alternative food network based on ecological and social justice principles.

Specific **goals** within these topics include transforming seed management (e.g., Red de Semillas Libres de Colombia), cultivating and preserving ancient wheat varieties that are drought- and weather- resistant (e.g., Al-Barakah Wheat project from Amman, Jordan, Example 5) and realising “strong governance” between the government and citizens while tackling connected issues, such as water scarcity, land fragmentation, food security, gender equity and poverty alleviation (e.g., Seoul Food Citizens Committee, South Korea, Example 6).

Moreover, many initiatives have experienced changing roles throughout their **trajectories**. Some, such as the Al-Barakah Wheat project (Example 5) and the Arab Network for Food Sovereignty (Example 22), have stayed relatively specific to their initial cause, while others, such as La Via Campesina (Example 12), have developed extensive networks to address diverse yet related issues.

Furthermore, the **scale of operation** may differ significantly with many FPNs operating at the local and municipal level, other being active at regional level, while some even extend their activities to the national and international level (see figure 4).

FPNs also differ in **size of membership**. Some are small, comprising less than 15 members, and often concern standing committees or councils, while others are large international networks comprising over 100,000 members (see figure 5).

Figure 4. Examples of the different scales of FPNs

Figure 5. Examples of the range in size of FPN membership

Example 3: Syracuse-Onondaga Food Systems Alliance (SOFSA), USA

FPN type: FPN with government; includes local government, healthcare, higher education, non-profit organisations and stakeholders across the food system.

Aim: To strengthen the food system for all people in Syracuse and Onondaga County; to unite communities to foster relationships, develop projects, align resources in equitable ways and advocate for policies to improve the health of people and the environment.

Background: Established in 2019, the grassroots coalition emerged as a result of a food system assessment called FoodPlanCNY (Central New York). The network has grown to include an advisory board, over 30 member organisations and 350+ newsletter subscribers.

Sources: <https://syfoodalliance.org/>; [Annual Report](#)

Example 4: Milan Pact Steering Committee de Córdoba, Spain

FPN type: Committee; members include local politicians and civil servants from Environment, Trade, Participation, Health and Social Services, companies, the Andalusian Regional Government, the Association of Organic Traders, organic producers, chefs, NGOs and the University of Córdoba (as coordinator).

Aim: To review the strategy and formulate action proposals consistent and adapted to the administration.

Background: Created in 2017 following a meeting between the food movement and the coalition government in 2016 that resulted in the city signing the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact. To meet this commitment, a diagnosis of the agri-food system was conducted, a governance space was created, and the Milan Pact Coordination Committee agreed on actions and decision-making procedures.

Sources: Vara-Sánchez, et al., 2021; <https://alimentandocordoba.es/>

Example 5: Al-Barakah Wheat project from Amman, Jordan

FPN type: FPN with government; consisting of the City of Amman, a social enterprise, farmers, rural producers, a local bakery, and citizens and schools who run activities through the network.

Aim: To: 1) increase urban agriculture production, 2) cultivate and preserve ancient wheat varieties that are drought and weather resistant, 3) bridge the divide between rural and urban spaces, and 4) promote the concept of food sovereignty in the Arab region.

Background: Al-Barakah Wheat project began in 2019 as an offshoot from the social enterprise, Zikra for Popular Learning. Their work is part of a grassroots movement to grow an urban farming collective of ancient wheat varieties that connect these producers directly to bakeries in the city.

Sources: Tohme Tawk et al., n.d; de Zeeuw, H. et al., 2017.

Example 6: Seoul Food Citizens Committee, South Korea

FPN type: Committee; composed of 111 members and 7 subcommittees with government representatives from the Mayor's office, policy planning, women and family division, welfare policy, education and health. Citizen representatives include NGOs, companies, food producers, community leaders and academics.

Aim: To realize 'strong governance' with citizens; the wider 'Seoul Green Vision 21' includes objectives in 8 areas, including (food) waste, water, air, transportation, urban planning, ecosystems, culture and welfare.

Background: The first committee was formed in 2017 along with the Food Ordinance and Food Master Plan development, followed by a survey and urban food policy conference in 2018. In 2019, a food strategy/vision was established. The City's actions to tackle food waste have led to a 10% reduction annually.

Sources: Jin-sook, 2022.

Example 7: Antananarivo Food Policy Council (AFPC), Madagascar

FPN type: FPC with government; driven by the city council, includes farmers, consumers, industry, food vendors and markets.

Aim: Established to develop micro-gardens in vulnerable neighbourhoods to address concerns of food insecurity and encourage income-generating activities. This focus has since extended to implement the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact.

Background: Initiated in 2014 through a multi-actor platform created with the intention of strengthening and connecting actions on urban food security. Evolved into a FPC after signing the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact. Initially funded by cooperation grants by the French region, île-de-France, it has since become more prioritised with support of RUAF (Global Partnership on Urban Agriculture and Food Systems) and the Food and Agriculture Organization.

Sources: One Planet. n.d.

Example 8: Australia's Right to Food Coalition, Australia

FPN type: A nation-wide coalition of organisations, practitioners, health and community workers and researchers.

Aim: To: 1) facilitate networking for collective impact.; 2) identify areas for policy research and areas for action; 3) undertake advocacy on right to food issues; and 4) communicate best practice research and activities in Australia and beyond.

Background: Began in 2014 after a conference, with the national Coalition being established in 2016. The Coalition has since organised events and initiatives that include: developing position statements for advocacy; taking over the work of Sydney Fair Food Alliance that used to be a leading group; and participating in the NSW Senate Enquiry into Fresh Food Pricing.

Sources: Barbour, et al., 2017 ; Lindberg, et al., 2016; RTF, 2021; Wood et al., 2018; <https://righttofood.org.au/>.

Example 9: Solidary Ecological Group¹, Istria and Zagreb, Croatia

FPN type: Solidarity economy/community supported agriculture network (CSA); composed of citizens, immigrants, farmers, direct-supply initiatives, far-Left representatives, consumers, small farmers, activist groups and organic agriculture certifiers

Aim: To propose an alternative to the utilitarian economic model for essential goods

Background: An informal initiative that formed in response to the multi-year debt and austerity crisis in the EU starting in 2010. Operations started in both regions in 2012 as the 'RA.ME Association', with the CSA starting in 2009. The Zagreb CSA was based on mutual trust and transparency in opposition to certification schemes, while the Istria CSA changed their name to 'Solidary Ecological Group' to set itself apart from non-certified groups

Sources: Orlic et al., 2022

¹The name of the organisation has been changed to protect its anonymity, but the form, an abbreviation, resembles the original.

Example 10: African Food Security Urban Network, Southern Africa

FPN type: FPN with government; includes society, academia and business.

Aim: To influence national and municipal policy affecting food security by improving the knowledge base of urban food insecurity in Africa.

Background: Founded in 2008 to address food insecurity in Africa's rapidly growing towns and cities. Subsequent phases aim to expand network to the rest of Africa.

Sources: Crush et al., 2011; <https://afsun.org/>; <https://scholars.wlu.>

4. A FOCUS ON VULNERABLE AND MARGINALISED GROUPS AND TRANSFORMATIONAL CAPACITY

The food environment can have a significant impact on vulnerable and marginalised groups in either negative or positive ways, where certain “groups tend to face systemic and institutional constraints, and are often left behind by governments and other stakeholders (such as the private sector) and disempowered within the food system” (Gaupp et al., 2021: 928). Through their cross-sectoral and trans-local actions, FPNs can help steer and shape the state of food environments to support greater food accessibility, equality and empowerment (Pineo, 2020). In Section 4.1, we explore which groups FPNs are helping and how. In section 4.2, we analyse the transformational capacity of FPNs. A conceptual framework is introduced to identify this capacity of FPNs at three different levels.

4.1 FPNs’ ENGAGEMENT WITH VULNERABLE AND MARGINALISED GROUPS

This review reflects a **high diversity of target groups** are being supported by FPNs. These groups are highly contextual to each region’s pressures and situations, such as times of war, climate change or other crises. Rather than state they wish to engage with specific vulnerable and marginalised groups, **many FPNs refer to the general goal** of supporting food insecure (small-scale, urban and peri-urban, part-time) farmers, women, indigenous groups, youth or refugees.

They cite goals such as:

- **Social justice, diversity, equity and inclusivity** (as in the case of the Ottawa County Food Policy Council, Canada, Example 18);
- **Tackling urban food poverty** (as indicated by the Ghent Food Council, Belgium, Example 14);
- **Helping gain access to land** (such as the National Association of Small Farmers, Cuba, Example 16); or,
- **Informing national sustainable food policies** (as is shown in the Ernährungszukunft Schweiz, Switzerland, Example 15).

Table 5 below provides examples of engagement with vulnerable and marginalised groups from the selected FPN examples.

Table 5: A focus on vulnerable and marginalised groups from selected FPN examples

<p>E.g. 1: Birmingham Food Policy Council, UK</p> <p>Who: Marginalised groups are a focal point in the council's reports. However, they are referred to in general terms, such as the food insecure, school or women's programs.</p> <p>How: They highlight the social inequities of food security, food inflation, and labour exploitation in the UK food system.</p>	<p>E.g. 2: Sustain Ontario's Municipal Food Policy Network, Canada</p> <p>Who: Farmers and farm workers, indigenous communities.</p> <p>How: Their policy advocacy work includes the right to food, support for new entry farmers, and addressing exploitative and precarious labour conditions for farm workers. Sustain includes indigenous groups and councils in their networks such as hosting joint conferences on food.</p>	<p>E.g. 3: Syracuse-Onondaga Food Systems Alliance (SOFSA), USA</p> <p>Who: LGBTQ+, BIPoC, people with a low-income ((i.e., communities of color, women, and immigrants)</p> <p>How: They facilitate inclusive networks by holding meetings to engage with LGBTQ+ and BIPoC communities. The alliance has also launched a food justice fund; a community-driven participatory grantmaking process that supports small-scale food justice projects for people historically excluded from economic resources.</p>
<p>E.g. 4: Milan Pact Steering Committee de Córdoba, Spain</p> <p>Who: Participants of schools, canteens, hospital and food aid, and local farmers.</p> <p>How: One objective is the right to healthy and sustainable food which includes "The public purchase of sustainable food, as well as the commitment of school and social canteens, hospitals and food aid entities for a healthier and more sustainable diet, contributes to improving the health of people and the planet, while supporting the local production, key to the future of our environment."</p>	<p>E.g. 5: Al-Barakah Wheat project from Amman, Jordan</p> <p>Who: Families in need.</p> <p>How: They allocate 10% of the total wheat harvest from their urban plots to support families in need. The wheat harvest is available through donation.</p>	<p>E.g. 6: Seoul Food Citizens Committee, South Korea</p> <p>Who: Referred to as Seoul's "food citizens" (Jin-sook, 2022).</p> <p>How: They place emphasis on the 'Fundamental Food Rights of Seoul Citizens', by including public meal support and run the Nutrition Plus Project to improve food and nutritional security.</p>
<p>E.g. 7: Antananarivo Food Policy Council (AFPC), Madagascar</p>	<p>E.g. 8: Australia's Right to Food Coalition, Australia</p>	<p>E.g. 9: Solidary Ecological Group, Istria and Zagreb, Croatia</p>

<p>Who: Students, youth and women.</p> <p>How: Works closely with NGOs and civil society organisations to address a wide range of social and developmental issues, such as school feeding schemes and vegetable gardens, nutritional education in schools, early childhood development and women's empowerment.</p>	<p>Who: To improve the health and wellbeing of all Australians.</p> <p>How: By working to ensure equitable access to nutritious food, including supporting people on welfare benefits (RTF, 2021).</p>	<p>Who: To support households affected by the austerity measures, including immigrants as well as small local farmers.</p> <p>How: To provide alternative economic model to access essential goods.</p>
<p>E.g. 10: African Food Security Urban Network, Southern Africa</p> <p>Who: Focuses on HIV/AIDS related challenges that affect food security.</p> <p>How: Activities involve assessing policies, identifying regulatory obstacles, creating gender and environmentally conscious food security plans for each city, delivering training to officials, hosting policy workshops on urban food security issues and publishing policy-oriented materials.</p>	<p>E.g. 11: City Strategic Agenda for Amman, Jordan</p> <p>Who: To improve the livelihoods of the urban poor.</p> <p>How: By installing rooftop garden projects in low-income neighborhoods to provide extra income for residents and encourage trade of urban agriculture under a label guarantee for product quality.</p>	<p>E.g. 12: La Via Campesina, global</p> <p>Who: Peasants, a strong focus on women's rights and gender equality.</p> <p>How: It seeks to empower peasants by using "diálogo de saberes", a dialog of different knowledges and ways of knowing from different rural cultures across the globe. Members participate in agroecology and political leadership training at peasant schools and faculties (Motta 2021; Martínez-Torres and Rosset 2014). They have a growing number of female leaders, strategies to achieve gender parity in decision making, and prominent campaigns on violence against women and food security, sovereignty and gender (Bhattacharjya et al., 2013).</p>
<p>E.g. 13: Food Liaison Advisory Groups (FLAG), Nairobi and Kisumu, Kenya</p> <p>Who: A strong focus on youth and women street food vendors.</p> <p>How: By providing training opportunities to develop the skills of youth in specific food value chains such as fish, vegetables and poultry. In Kisumu, there has been a</p>	<p>E.g. 14: Gent en Garde, Ghent, Belgium</p> <p>Who: Focuses on those experiencing urban food poverty.</p> <p>How: The council partners with a network of civil society organisations to facilitate projects that seek to empower vulnerable groups in the city. For example, The Site, utilizes publicly owned land to run a social grocery</p>	<p>E.g. 15: Ernährungszukunft Schweiz, Switzerland</p> <p>Who: Focuses on selecting a representative sample of the Swiss resident population with specific attention to youth and intergenerational justice.</p> <p>How: Participants for the citizen assembly were selected based on a random sample of 80 individuals from across the entire Swiss resident population. The</p>

<p>focus on supporting women street food vendors through business opportunities and tackling issues related to food safety and sanitation.</p>	<p>store offering affordable and locally grown fresh produce in a low-income neighborhood.</p>	<p>aim was to be as representative as possible in terms of age, gender and language. They also had focused on youth and intergenerational justice in the activities of the assembly.</p>
<p>E.g. 16: Asociación Nacional de Agricultores Pequeños, Cuba</p> <p>Who: Peasants, small-scale farmers and small agricultural cooperatives.</p> <p>How: It seeks to provide technical and economic assistance to its members through training programs and educational opportunities. The association also acts as a voice for Cuban peasants and farmers in political spaces, specifically regarding national policies on agriculture.</p>	<p>E.g. 17: Colectivo Agroecológico and the Movimiento de Economía Social y Solidaria (MESSE), Ecuador</p> <p>Who: Peasants, small-scale farmers and small agricultural cooperatives.</p> <p>How: The collective participated in the Day of Peasant Struggle as a solidarity act with Ecuadorian peasants. They also participate in policy spaces to advocate for food sovereignty, peasant agriculture and agrobiodiversity.</p>	<p>E.g. 18: Ottawa Food Policy Council, Ottawa, Canada</p> <p>Who: Youth</p> <p>How: They emphasize intergenerational justice at the intersection of youth and food policy. The council recently formed a new Ottawa Youth Food Policy Council gives youth from across the Ottawa territory a space in local food system governance.</p>
<p>E.g. 19: Ons eten Den Haag, The Hague, Netherlands</p> <p>Who: Local residents facing urban food insecurity, youth and elderly.</p> <p>How: Through policy briefs, they seek to advocate for healthy and affordable food as a basic right for everyone in the city.</p>	<p>E.g. 20: Le Début des Haricots, Brussels, Belgium</p> <p>Who: Small-scale farmers, peasants and low-income residents.</p> <p>How: They have a strong focus on supporting small-scale local farmers and peasants in the city through social, economic, and educational forms of assistance. In 2023, the network started a citizen food subsistence project targeting social housing sites across Belgium.</p>	<p>E.g. 21: Brighton & Hove Food Partnership, UK</p> <p>Who: Individuals in need and people with disabilities.</p> <p>How: The partnership offers community cookery sessions that support mental health and the development of life skills for individuals in need from across the city. They also distribute educational materials and recipe kits to low-income households. Through four community gardens, the partnership hosts dementia-friendly gardening sessions. Following a consulting session on internal equalities and diversity, the partnership created a working group to address the lack of racial diversity in the partnership.</p>

<p>E.g. 22: Arab Network for Food Sovereignty, Middle East Region</p> <p>Who: Small-scale farmers, fishermen, women and youth.</p> <p>How: All members of the network take part in electing new representatives to the executive committee every three years. A major focus on marginalised groups comes through their advocacy work, like warning of collapsing food systems in Gaza as a result of Israeli bombings, relieving farmers of debt burdens incurred during COVID-19, and supporting small-scale producers through opening markets and exempting them from taxes. They also focus on advocating for the rights of peasants and farmers in the region by joining campaigns and events from La Via Campesina (Example 12).</p>	<p>E.g. 23: Food Change Lab, global</p> <p>Who: Inclusion of citizen voices, particularly ‘missing voices’ such as women, youth, farmers, street food vendors, students and day labourers.</p> <p>How: They place emphasis on bringing diverse stakeholders, both experts and everyday citizens, to shape local food systems in a more inclusive manner. The food change lab in Fort Portal, Uganda, focuses specifically on the needs of street food vendors. Through their advocacy work, food vendors received more formal recognition from public authorities alongside improved infrastructure, such as street lights, access to water and designated areas for vending (Pittore & Debons, 2023).</p>	<p>E.g. 24: Working Group for Food for Change, Bangkok, Thailand</p> <p>Who: Street and market vendors, urban farmers</p> <p>How: The working group provides material support to urban farmers through the free distribution of seeds and other farming resources, routes to local markets for their produce, and protective policies and regulatory frameworks. Their work has facilitated the expansion of urban gardens in poorer communities throughout Bangkok in partnership with other civil society-based organisations, such as the City Farm Association.</p>
--	---	--

The assessment suggests that African FPNs are an exception to this rule. They often specify target groups. Many African FPNs are established in **response to a lack of inclusive decision-making to address food and nutrition insecurity**. Consequently, many African FPNs place a strong emphasis on inclusive governance to empower marginalised voices and advance food and nutrition security for all (e.g., Food Change Lab in Fort Portal, Uganda and Zambia, Example 23). This is generally done through holding workshops, community meetings, establishing forums and contributing to policy formulation through consultation with marginalised stakeholders. Many of these initiatives are established or initiated by international NGOs and/or multilateral organisations, such as the Food and Agriculture Organization, the German Government Agency for International Cooperation, Rikolto and the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact. In fact, most of the reviewed FPNs in Africa were initiated as part of developmental projects and many of the same actors initiate similar actions in different cities and countries.

African FPN examples that target specific vulnerable and marginalised groups include:

- **School feeding schemes and vegetable gardens, nutritional education in schools and social centers, early childhood development, women empowerment (e.g., the Antananarivo Food Policy Council, Madagascar, Example 7);**
- **Attending to HIV/AIDS related challenges that affect food security (e.g., African Food Security Urban Network, southern Africa, Example 10);**
- **Initiatives to enable youth and women's upliftment and empowerment (e.g., Nairobi and Environs Food Security, Agriculture and Livestock Forum, Kenya).**
- **Focused on the needs of women street food vendors (e.g., Food Liaison Advisory Groups (FLAG), Nairobi and Kisumu, Kenya, Example 13).**

In the Middle East, the involvement of marginal groups varies amongst the FPNs reviewed. For example, in Jordan, marginal groups were considered more as targeted beneficiaries to be empowered rather than as partners in the policy network or policymaking process. Urban agriculture is the main focal point of the FPN, which designates a certain amount of funds towards developing food growing projects in low-income neighbourhoods. The City Strategic Agenda from Jordan (Example 11) is one such example that seeks to improve the livelihoods and wellbeing of the urban poor by installing rooftop gardens. Alternatively, the Arab Network for Food Sovereignty (Example 22) actively involves small-scale farmers, fishermen, women and youth in the internal election processes of organisational representatives while also focusing on territories in conflict and protracted security situations in the region.

In North America, almost all the selected projects focus on improving the conditions for vulnerable and/or marginal groups, including migrant workers (documented and undocumented), low-income households, homeless individuals, refugees, food insecure households, people with disabilities and Native Americans. The Evansville Area Food Council is one example that targets

undocumented migrants, documented immigrants, refugees, Native Americans, people with little or no income and/or without permanent living arrangements and food insecure households.

Example 11: City Strategic Agenda for Amman, Jordan

FPN type: Agenda; includes the Municipality of Greater Amman, citizens, farmers, civil organisations, universities, private sector companies and other governmental entities.

Aim: To prioritise actions for the 2010 City Strategic Agenda that will tackle issues of water scarcity, land fragmentation, food security, gender equity and poverty alleviation.

Background: Born out of a study that resulted in establishing working groups to support the City Strategic Agenda. The city decided to institutionalise an office for resources in 2007, eventually adopting the City Strategic Agenda and introducing new legislation. Priorities included: 15% of all surfaces should be dedicated to green spaces and/or home gardens, to incorporate urban agriculture into the new master plan in Amman, and to restrict the re-zoning of agricultural land in the city for non-agricultural use.

Sources: Cauchois et al., 2014; de Zeeuw, et al.; 2017, Tohme Tawk et al., n.d.

Example 12: La Via Campesina, global

FPN type: A transnational food movement; Composed of national, regional and continental alliances and organisations of peasant and family farmers and indigenous people.

Aim: To defend small-scale sustainable agriculture, to promote social justice and dignity, to farm in harmony with nature and to oppose agribusiness and transnational companies that hurt ecosystems.

Background: Was formally constituted in Mons, Belgium in 1993 as a precursor to the Uruguay Round of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade, which represented a shift towards a market-driven global economy.

Sources: Martínez-Torres and Rosset, 2014

Example 13: Food Liaison Advisory Groups (FLAG), Nairobi and Kisumu, Kenya

FPN type: Advisory group; includes food system stakeholders, public sectors, civil society organizations, academic institutions and development partners.

Aim: To identify food system challenges, create solutions through integrated approaches and advising public officials on sustainable food system planning.

Background: FLAGs in both Nairobi and Kisumu were formed with the support of the United Nations Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO). In Nairobi, the FLAG was initiated by the local government who later institutionalized the group through the county legislation. In Kisumu, the FLAG emerged as a result of a food system forum and has since been instrumental in major government food plans and research activities.

Sources: [Nairobi County Food Strategy.pdf](#); [Kisumu's FLAG](#)

In FPNs in **Australian and New Zealand** a focus on food security prevails, **where food security is often based on food redistribution practices**, in addition to supporting the right to food. Australia's Right to Food Coalition (Example 8) is one example that seeks to improve the health and wellbeing of all Australians. Another focus both in **Australian and Central and South American** FPNs is to assist **farmers** that face repression or vulnerabilities in their existence. For instance, the Australian Food Sovereignty Alliance recognises the impact of powerful supermarket chains on independent farmers. In Central and South America, many FPNs, such as the Colectivo Agroecológico and the Movimiento de Economía Social y Solidaria in Ecuador (Example 17), focus on supporting food sovereignty, agroecology, peasant and indigenous agriculture and women farmers.

FPNs in the **Mediterranean region share a similar focus as elsewhere. Their measures often address asylum seekers, refugees, children, women, low-income households and small-scale farmers.** FPNs in this region also recognise **the “new”** working poor and middle-class households, which are losing their purchasing power. FPNs in Mediterranean countries often place attention on guaranteeing access to healthy food to all. For example, the Solidary Ecological Group in Croatia (Example 9) seeks to help people who have been affected by the multi-year debt and austerity crisis in the EU, including immigrant households and small farmers.

Example 14: Gent en Garde, Ghent, Belgium

FPN type: Food Policy Council; including 30 representatives from across food system sectors, civil society and the public sector.

Aim: To provide policy recommendations and implement sustainable food projects.

Background: In 2013, public authorities legislated the Gent en Garde as a mechanism to collaborate towards a sustainable food agenda for Ghent. The council was instrumental in forming the city's food strategy. Since 2018, the council has received a specific budget to support innovative food projects that align with its strategic goals.

Sources: Prove et al., 2019; [Gent en Garde Website](#)

Example 15: Ernährungszukunft Schweiz, Switzerland

FPN type: Science-Citizen Assembly that includes FPCs, academics, 80 randomly selected citizens and government bodies.

Aim: To envision what a sustainable food policy for Switzerland could look like in 2030.

Background: In 2022, three Swiss Food Policy Councils organized the 'Food Future Switzerland' consortium that included a Citizens' Council for Food Policy. Throughout 2022, the citizens' council convened multiple times to develop food policy recommendations that were then delivered to government bodies at the National Nutrition Summit in 2023.

Sources: <https://ernaehrungs-zukunft.ch/>

Example 16: Asociación Nacional de Agricultores Pequeños, Cuba

FPN type: A nation-wide association of small farmers, agricultural cooperatives and peasants.

Aim: To organize Cuban peasants in their participation in the social and economic transformation of the rural environment.

Background: The association was formed in 1961 and has since been regarded as one of the most important rural associations representing the interests and needs of Cuban peasants and farmers. It is structured as a network of cooperatives that brings together over 300,000 members.

Sources: <http://www.campesinocubano.cu/>

Example 17: Colectivo Agroecológico and the Movimiento de Economía Social y Solidaria (MESSE), Ecuador

FPN type: Collective; civil society organisations, associations and groups of farmers, citizen-consumers, advocates of agroecology and food sovereignty.

Aim: To promote awareness and campaigns, policy advocacy and conduct agroecological training.

Background: In 2007, MESSE emerged as a result of a collaborative effort of five groups promoting agroecology in Ecuador: UTOPÍA (Chimborazo), the Mar Tierra y Canasta Network, the PROBIO Producers Association, The Seed Guardians Network and the Ecuadorian Coordinator of Agroecology (CEA). Since then, they have hosted 13 national meetings with members and seven agroecological conferences.

Sources: <https://colectivoagroecologico.org/quienessomos/>

Example 18: Ottawa Food Policy Council, Ottawa, Canada

FPN type: FPC; seven members currently make up its membership composition with backgrounds in policy, research, education, nutrition and law.

Aim: To 1) analyse policy proposals with a holistic food system lens considering both rural and urban realities in Ottawa; 2) facilitate connections across Ottawa's food network; 3) enhance public participation in food policy; and 4) cooperate with decision-making bodies in implementing food policies.

Background: The FPC emerged out of a need for a more collaborative and bottom-up approach towards food issues in the city. It sought to bring together different areas of expertise alongside the voice of the public to inform local food policy.

Sources: <https://ofpc-cpao.ca/>

4.2 THE TRANSFORMATIONAL CAPACITY OF FPNs

This section examines FPNs' capacity to initiate and support policy change in the food environment **as a leverage point** to transform the food system. We contextualise the transformative capacity of FPNs on den Boer et al.'s (2023)² framework of change on three levels:

- **Non-systemic intermediation in-between individual entities:** actions that occur between “individual actors, organizations or projects” to gain information or knowledge or access to resources;
- **Systemic intermediation facilitating ‘horizontal interactions’:** actions that occur between entities within a single network and between entities from different networks with the same goals, such as the exchange of knowledge that can catalyse activities within and between networks;
- **Systemic intermediation facilitating ‘vertical interactions’:** actions that occur between actor networks and between their related institutions to initiate or support institutional change processes. Here, norms, values, and laws, regulations and standards may be disrupted, stimulating “new visions and expectations, initiating policy renewal, and acting as an impartial voice for new networks of actors”).

Table 6 collates the transformational efforts of the combined regional reviews of FPNs.

Table 6: The transformational capacity of the FPNs following the framework by Den Boer et al., 2023.

1. NON-SYSTEMIC INTERMEDIATION IN-BETWEEN INDIVIDUAL ENTITIES

- **In Spain**, all reviewed FPNs focus on education projects and awareness campaigns. For example, Valencia has created a map to make the heritage of local food producers and fisherfolk more visible, complemented by several campaigns and activities. Only Madrid has provided more direct action on public canteens of nursery schools as part of the Madrid Agroecological Platform.
- **In North America and Canada**, all reviewed FPNs claim to be working towards some form of transformation. Most are concerned with creating co-benefits across the different elements of sustainability, although a small number focus on one of these elements. Transformation is mainly evident in relation to food systems but some mention broader – economic, social or environmental – forms of transformation that extend beyond the food system. All the FPNs are working with partners to connect food with other policy areas and/or priorities.
- **In Germany**, the reviewed FPNs are filling in gaps in governance by allowing migrants to integrate and participate in society and food culture.

² This work draws on the work of Kanda et al. (2020) related to systemic activities of intermediaries in sustainability transitions.

- **In Belgium**, one FPN, Le Début des Haricots (Example 20), centralises knowledge transfer opportunities around alternative and innovative forms of farming.
- **In Austria**, the focus of the reviewed FPN in Vienna is mainly on educational projects that target different groups such as children, students or public procurement staff members.
- **In Thailand**, the FPN found in Bangkok (Example 24) had a transformational focus on empowerment through land ownership and by providing a voice in local zoning.
- **In South Korea**, the FPN in Seoul targets food access.

2. SYSTEMIC INTERMEDIATION FACILITATING “HORIZONTAL INTERACTIONS”

- **In Africa**, many reviewed FPNs respond to transformation by directly engaging with stakeholders that are most severely impacted by unsustainable and unjust food systems in the development of solutions to these issues. Through this they build mutually beneficial relationships between actors within and beyond contexts – this is a key aspect of the type of transformation they drive.
- **The reviewed FPNs in Senegal (CIGA), Kenya (FLAGS) and Madagascar** play a key role in building and strengthening inter-city cooperation and coordination and linkages between rural and urban areas.
- **In Australia**, reviewed FPNs are providing actual alternative marketplaces, are attempting to change small-scale processing laws and are striving to prevent/protect urbanisation into farming regions, often through research and horizontal collaboration efforts.
- **In England**, the Brighton & Hove Food Partnership (Example 21) formed a city-wide emergency food network of over 50 organisations to provide low-cost, healthy food to individuals in need.

3. SYSTEMIC INTERMEDIATION FACILITATING “VERTICAL INTERACTIONS”

- **In Amman, Jordan and Carthage, Tunisia**, reviewed FPNs are looking to practically transform urban land use plans through policy to integrate a food sensitive approach, such as for FPNs.
- **In Australia**, the reviewed FPNs have a keen involvement in the national legislature (such as white papers), as well as being very active in food waste legislation.
- **In Central and South America** - Solidarity networks have significant policy impacts. For example, La Via Campesina provides “the voice of peasant organizations/farmers”; facilitates identity of peasants as anti-capitalist and as a peasant class; promotes alliances and mobilisation around seed, GMO, free trade agreements and the World Trade Organization.
- **In Turin and Zagreb**, reviewed FPNs such as RECUP are aiming to overcome traditional approaches.
- **In Milan and Bergamo**, reviewed FPNs are pursuing integration for holistic change.
- **In Zagreb and Rome**, reviewed FPNs are catalysing change from bottom-up towards higher recognition and political buy-in.

Table 7 below provides more detailed examples of transformational capacity from the case studies.

Table 7: A focus on transformational capacity from the selected FPN examples

<p>1: Birmingham Food Policy Council, UK</p> <p>A main activity is to produce multi-media reports (i.e., policy briefs, landscape maps, and podcasts) in response to local and national government strategies and plans around food systems. These reports look to increase awareness by critically assessing plans and policies for future action. The council also produces thinking tools for food system scenarios to support decision-making processes about the future of food in the UK.</p>	<p>2: Sustain Ontario's Municipal Food Policy Network, Canada</p> <p>This FPN was a key actor in developing the 2014 Ontario Food and Nutrition Strategy. They have also developed policy briefs targeting key issues in the Ontario food system, such as the Food Literacy for Students Act 2020. Sustain also facilitates multi-stakeholder networks and working groups covering topics such as protecting farming and farmland, building sustainable food enterprises and developing food education networks.</p>	<p>3: Syracuse-Onondaga Food Systems Alliance (SOFSA), USA</p> <p>In 2022, SOFSA helped secure over 1.6 million dollars for their partners who run projects supporting food access and food sovereignty. Also, they succeeded in increasing state funding for Double Up Food Bucks (a food access program in the region). They also train citizens to engage with policymakers on food system issues.</p>
<p>4: Milan Pact Steering Committee de Córdoba, Spain</p> <p>These include training actions for technical personnel and practical lessons shared in the Network of Cities for Agroecology. Through 'Alimentando Cordoba', they have conducted several awareness campaigns and educational programs focusing on agroecology, health and sustainable diets. They also aim to create a local network of businesses.</p>	<p>5: Al-Barakah Wheat project from Amman, Jordan</p> <p>They encourage urban agricultural production, creating local procurement schemes and educational activities for youth.</p>	<p>6: Seoul Food Citizens Committee, South Korea</p> <p>This includes institutional buy-in and a 'strong government' approach; winner of the special award from the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact.</p>

<p>7: Antananarivo Food Policy Council (AFPC), Madagascar</p> <p>The city council adopted a policy as practice approach, placing and prioritising the AFPC at the center of it. The city council's role is designed to continue through political changes. Diverse projects have emerged that have increased shared ownership, improving sustainable production, procurement and access to markets.</p>	<p>8: Australia's Right to Food Coalition, Australia</p> <p>Contributing to policy outcomes, such as in the pre-budget submission (RTF 2021), they state: "to support calls ... to permanently raise the rate of welfare payments", particularly for people currently ineligible for support, such as international students and asylum seekers.</p>	<p>9: Solidary Ecological Group, Istria and Zagreb, Croatia</p> <p>The CSAs are now included within regional policies and have each received differing amounts of support from regional and local institutions. Like many other CSAs, both CSAs uphold solidarity, sharing and non-consumerist principles.</p>
<p>10: African Food Security Urban Network, Southern Africa</p> <p>Aims to impact national and municipal food security policy through four strategies: 1. lobbying and advocating within established networks related to food security, HIV/AIDS, environment (built and natural) and urban poverty; 2. engaging at the local level to shape the city agenda, foster stakeholder collaboration and raise awareness about urban food security and HIV concerns; 3. building the capacity of food security experts who will actively participate in policy initiatives; and 4. generating dependable data to influence the thinking and responses of policymakers and implementers.</p>	<p>11: City Strategic Agenda for Amman, Jordan</p> <p>It directly influenced legislation on land use planning and zoning of agricultural areas by incorporating urban agriculture in future urban master plans and committing the city to an agenda on urban agriculture. Their work is included in other strategic documents, such as the Amman Resilience Strategy, which aims at increasing urban and rooftop agriculture and organising an urban food fest of Amman, promoting the city's food heritage and promoting social cohesion.</p>	<p>12: La Via Campesina, global</p> <p>LVC became the voice of and gave an identity to peasant organisations and farmers. They also promoted international mobilisations focused on topics such as seed, GMOs, and free trade agreements, leading to the creation of alliances around the world. LVC has succeeded in internationally promoting food sovereignty and contributed to establishing the Convention of the United Nations on Peasant Rights (Nicholson and Borras 2023).</p>

<p>13: Food Liaison Advisory Groups (FLAG), Nairobi and Kisumu, Kenya</p> <p>FLAG has influenced the county-legislated food strategies for Nairobi and Kisumu, respectively. FLAG has provided coordination and leadership in the food governance space to effectively mobilise resources, develop innovative integrated policy approaches and facilitate participatory governance mechanisms.</p>	<p>14: Gent en Garde, Ghent, Belgium</p> <p>Gent en Garde has been integral in catalysing the city's food strategy towards operational goals in terms of policy and project interventions. Moreover, the council leverages its financial resources to support innovative solutions to local food system challenges in the city.</p>	<p>15: Ernährungszukunft Schweiz, Switzerland</p> <p>They utilised democratic, participatory governance mechanisms to formulate policy recommendations for a sustainable food policy at the national level. The deliberative process design supported the democratic capacity development of citizens to actively participate in public decision-making processes around the food system.</p>
<p>16: Asociación Nacional de Agricultores Pequeños, Cuba</p> <p>The association provided a central organisational structure to support the collective action of Cuban peasants, farmers and their networks in transforming their social and economic circumstances. They also developed collective learning programs, most notably the 'Farmer to Farmer Agroecology Movement', where the association looked to scale agroecological food production. More than 200,000 peasant families have participated in this program</p>	<p>17: Colectivo Agroecológico and the Movimiento de Economía Social y Solidaria (MESSE), Ecuador</p> <p>Contributed to the movement towards agroecology and food sovereignty in Ecuador. The collective has succeeded in establishing itself as a network of networks to integrate the fragmented efforts of individuals and organisations towards a more sustainable food system.</p>	<p>18: Ottawa County Food Policy Council, Ottawa, Canada</p> <p>The council's work is largely focused on advocating transformative change through policy advocacy. They comment on and provide policy briefs on municipal, provincial, and federal policies, such as those on food waste and more circular food economies. They have also contributed to a more bottom-up approach to food governance by enhancing opportunities for public participation in decision-making processes.</p>

<p>19: Ons eten Den Haag, The Hague, Netherlands</p> <p>The FPN utilised the existing network of food movement actors to work towards a sustainable food transition in the municipality. After a period of advocating for an update to the outdated municipal food strategy, in the 2022-2026 new coalition agreement, the municipality agreed with the FPN to update the food strategy with public participation being a main priority.</p>	<p>20: Le Début des Haricots, Brussels, Belgium</p> <p>The program activities of the network have provided a practical example of diversified agriculture in urban and peri-urban areas for both professional food producers and citizen projects. They utilise all of their projects as forms of knowledge transfer and education opportunities focusing on farming and agricultural practices.</p>	<p>21: Brighton & Hove Food Partnership, UK</p> <p>The partnership was the driving force behind the creation of the city’s emergency food network, which now includes 51 organisations operating in 59 locations across the city. This network looks to provide low-cost, healthy food to residents in need in a dignified manner.</p>
<p>22: Arab Network for Food Sovereignty, Middle East Region</p> <p>Besides implementing projects throughout the Arab region, the network advocates for food and natural resource sovereignty in international policy circles. For example, they presented at multiple FAO conferences and attended high-level meetings with the UN Special Rapporteur on the Right to Food.</p>	<p>23: Food Change Lab, global</p> <p>The food change lab is designed to influence the local city agenda. In Uganda, for example, the food change lab, through raising awareness, has stimulated the utilisation of indigenous crops in the local food economy. In Zambia, the Lusaka Food Policy Council emerged from the work of the food change lab, which allowed the work to be institutionalised legislatively.</p>	<p>24: Working Group for Food for Change, Bangkok, Thailand</p> <p>Provided a space for meaningful participation of diverse groups of actors across Bangkok, such as informal vendors and subsistence farmers. The group leveraged context-specific factors to make change effectively, such as gaining political support from the late monarch.</p>

This report reveals that **most reviewed FPNs are located within the first rung of transformational capacity** where their policy influence is often limited to lobbying for the development of food strategies, without any direct influence on policy. However, FPN efforts are present also in the second and third rungs, where they push for policy change both through horizontal and vertical collaborations.

An example of the latter is outlined in the case of Amman (Example 11). This FPN highlights a focus on empowering people to lead transformative initiatives, in which for larger projects, such as rooftop farms, the investment is made by the urban resident with the technical support of the municipality. This includes lowering structural barriers, such as home licenses for businesses, and allowing the legalisation of informal professions to lower financial burdens for start-up businesses to target unemployed citizens, housewives or those with disabilities who cannot work outside the home. Such regulations include food processing services like jam, bakery and pickle production.

Alternatively, FPN examples, such as La Via Campesina demonstrate that it is possible to increase the membership, size and geographical spread and to strengthen specific campaigns to have an impact at policy level, while maintaining cohesion across associated networks (see Example 12).

Example 19: Ons eten Den Haag, The Hague, Netherlands

FPN type: FPN; includes twenty-five experts in fields related to food systems, nature, sustainable economy, education, healthcare and urban development.

Aim: To independently represent and act as a spokesperson for residents, initiatives and entrepreneurs from the Hague in matters related to healthy, fair and sustainable food.

Background: Originated as an initiative from the association Ons Eten ('Our Food') to represent the voices of residents in The Hague area.

Sources: <https://ons-eten.nl/haagsevoedselraad>

Example 20: Le Début des Haricots, Brussels, Belgium

FPN type: Alternative agriculture network made up of farmers, citizens, civil society organisations and neighbourhood committees.

Aim: Contribute to a fair and resilient agri-food system through developing urban peasant agriculture.

Background: Created in 2005 as a non-profit organisation with a horizontal, egalitarian structure. It received recognition from Brussels Environment in 2009 and transformed into a social and democratic enterprise in 2019.

Sources: <https://www.haricots.org/spip.php?article1>

Example 21: Brighton & Hove Food Partnership, UK

FPN type: Partnership composed of staff, volunteers, residents, community organisations, local businesses and statutory agencies.

Aim: To deliver a range of projects pertaining to cooking, community gardens, affordable food and food waste.

Background: The partnership was formed as an initiative by local residents in 2003. Since then, it has developed into a not-for-profit organisation that has delivered a range of projects and programs to over 15,000 residents in Brighton & Hove. It has received many awards for its work from independent bodies, such as the Brighton & Hove Business Awards.

Sources: <https://bhfood.org.uk/about-us/>

Example 22: Arab Network for Food Sovereignty, Middle East Region

FPN type: Regional Network; 30 non-governmental organisations and unions of farmers, fishermen, shepherds, food workers, women, youth and consumer associations across 13 Arab countries.

Aim: To 1) Enhance the role of civil society in fields of food security and agriculture; 2) Strengthen the cooperation and coordination of Arab, regional, and global networking to exchange expertise; and 3) Influence governmental and non-governmental policies and regulations on the local, national, and international levels to achieve food and natural resource sovereignty.

Background: First created in 2012 as a result of the work from a few Arab civil society organisations. The network has expanded significantly since its genesis in terms of the number of representatives involved in the network and the scope of the work.

Sources: <https://www.apnature.org/en/arab-network-food-sovereignty-anfs>

Example 23: Food Change Labs, global

FPN type: Lab; multi-stakeholder partnership with local food system actors in the respected localities.

Aim: To support concrete sustainable food system interventions across the three labs in Fort Portal, Uganda, Zambia and Indonesia.

Background: The change labs were convened in 2015 by the International Institute for Environment and Development, Hivos and local partners.

Sources: [Food Change Labs](#)

Example 24: Working Group for Food for Change, Bangkok, Thailand

FPN type: Working Group; includes twenty-five experts in fields related to food systems, nature, sustainable economy, education, healthcare and urban development.

Aim: To counteract the rise of industrial, processed food diets and provide environmental resilience to flood-prone urban areas with a focus on urban agriculture.

Background: A civil society organisation that is part of a wider informal network of actors working on food system change in Bangkok.

Sources: [Working Group for Food for Change](#)

5. CONCLUSIONS

This report is **one of the first to map the diversity of compositional forms of FPNs across the world**. Focusing on FPNs that intersect with policy and that have a connection with the urban and/or city-region, more than 100 examples were found, out of which 47 were shortlisted for more in-depth study. The shortlisted examples represented 43 compositional types. This sample illustrates that **many diverse compositions of FPNs exist all over the world**, going beyond the dominant assumed form of FPCs and FPNs. FPNs also differed in their relationship with government as well as the type and degree of stakeholder membership of the FPN and which stakeholder initiates the FPN. Furthermore, the analysis shows that FPNs are also very diverse in a range of other features, including topic, goal, scale, geographical spread and size of membership.

Acknowledging that FPNs are well-placed to provide significant improvements to local food environments, we also examined who and how FPNs were supporting vulnerable and marginalised communities. This review shows that these target groups are not necessarily the key focus for many FPNs and that, as a category, “marginal and vulnerable groups” include **a very broad demographic that reflects dynamic geographical contexts, pressures and crises**. FPNs that did target specific groups occurred in regions where a distinct health or social need was noted. The type of support often remains very general, ranging from providing resources, such as food donations and/or information, through to providing new tools and infrastructure for self-empowerment. This report shows that additional information is required to better understand the overall trends of how FPNs are engaging with diverse communities – a key topic to be explored in the forthcoming interviews.

With regards to the transformational capacity of FPNs, the report found that many FPNs stay within the first rung of impact (i.e. non-systemic intermediation in-between individual entities), where other FPNs examples demonstrate that **transformational policy change is possible, in terms of empowering participants, by increasing FPNs’ size, cohesion of networks and impact at the policy level**. Future research that investigates the links between compositional type – such as FPNs’ relationship with government, their degree of openness to membership and their membership type across the quadruple helix – and the ability of a FPN to transform the food environment is a much needed and exciting space from which to better understand and enact food system transformation. This report provides the base knowledge for such research to be continued.

6. REFERENCES

- Barbour, L., Rose, N., Montegriffo, E., Wingrove, K., Clarke, B., Browne, J. and Rundle, M. (2017) *The Human Right to Food*. A position statement by the Right to Food Coalition, finalised April 2016, reviewed 2017, Australia.
- Bhattacharjya, M., Birchall, J., Caro, P., Kelleher, D. and Sahasranaman, V. (2013) Why gender matters in activism: feminism and social justice movements, *Gender and Development* 21(2): 277-293.
- Cauchois, S., Abbot, M., Kanury, C., Cousyn, L. and Estrada, V.V. (2014) *Amman, Jordan. Urban agriculture: Finding multi-purpose Urban NEXUS solutions through collaborative action*. Urban NEXUS Case Story 2014 – 26, August, GIZ-ICLEI.
- Crush, J., Frayne, B., Drimie, S., and Caesar, M. (2011) *The HIV and Urban Food Security Nexus*. Kingston, ON and Cape Town: African Food Security Urban Network. Urban Food Security Series 5.
- de Zeeuw, H. and Dubbeling, M. (2015) Process and tools for multi-stakeholder planning of the urban agro-food system. In de Zeeuw, H. and Drechsel, P. (eds.) *Cities and Agriculture. Developing resilient urban food systems*. London and New York: Routledge. Pp.56-87.
- de Zeeuw, H. et al. (2017) A Geography of Rooftop Agriculture in 20 Projects. In: Orsini, F., Dubbeling, M., de Zeeuw, H., Gianquinto, G. (eds.) *Rooftop Urban Agriculture. Urban Agriculture*. Cham: Springer.
- den Boer, A.C.L., van der Valk, A. J.J., Regeer, B.J., and Broerse, J.E.W. (2023) Food policy networks and their potential to stimulate systemic intermediation for food system transformation, *Cities* 135: 104239.
- Edwards, F., Sonnino, R. and López Cifuentes, M. (2023) *Deliverable 2.1: Report on facilitators of and barriers to the development and implementation of evidence-based and integrated food policies and planning frameworks*, WP2 Mapping and gapping, University of Surrey, February, the UK.
- Gaupp, F., Ruggeri Laderchi, C., Lotze-Campen, H., et al. (2021) Food system development pathways for healthy, nature-positive and inclusive food systems, *Nature Food*, Dec; 2(12): 928-934. 10.1038/s43016-021-00421-7.
- Jin-sook, J. (2022) *Innovative and Inclusive Governance of the Seoul Food Policy*. Seoul Metropolitan Government.
- Kanda, W., Kuisma, M., Kivimaa, P., and Hjelm, O. (2020) Conceptualising the systemic activities of intermediaries in sustainability transitions, *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 36, 449–465. doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2020.01.002

- Lake, D. (2019) *Women's collective organizations: An opportunity for upward mobility. A case study of the Mezitli Women Producers Market in Turkey*. Penn Institute for Urban Research Series on Informality, Women's Collective Organizations: An Opportunity for Upward Mobility, USA.
- One Planet (n.d.) *National and Sub-National Food Systems MultiStakeholder Mechanisms: An Assessment of Experiences*. https://www.oneplanetnetwork.org/sites/default/files/2021-10/211018_
- Lindberg, R., Caraher, M. and Wingrove, K. (2016) Implementing the right to food in Australia, *Victorian Journal of Home Economics* 55(2): 25-29.
- Martínez-Torres, M.E. and Rosset, P.M. (2014) Diálogo de saberes in La Vía Campesina: food sovereignty and agroecology, *Journal of Peasant Studies* 41(6): 979-997.
- Motta, R. (2021) Social movements as agents of change: Fighting intersectional food inequalities, building food as webs of life, *The Sociological Review Monographs* 69(3): 603–625.
- Nicholson, P. and Saturnino M. B. Jr. (2023) It wasn't an intellectual construction: the founding of La Via Campesina, achievements and challenges – a conversation, *The Journal of Peasant Studies*. 10.1080/03066150.2023.2174856
- Orlić, O., Časni, A. Č. and Dumančić, K. (2022) Practising Solidarity and Developing Food Citizenship in Croatia: The Example of Croatian Community-Supported Agriculture. In: Travlou, P. and Ciolfi, L. (eds.) *Ethnographies of Collaborative Economies across Europe: Understanding Sharing and Caring*. London: Ubiquity Press. doi.org/10.5334/bct.125.
- Pineo, H. (2020) Towards healthy urbanism: inclusive, equitable and sustainable (THRIVES) – an urban design and planning framework from theory to praxis, *Cities & Health*.
- Pittore, K. & Debons, P. (2023). Operationalizing Food System Governance: The Case of Fort Portal Food Change Lab. *Sustainability*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15043527>
- (RTF) Right to Food (2021) *Pre-budget submission 2021-22 Submission to Treasury*. Australia's Right to Food Coalition, January.
- Santo, R., Bassarab, K., Kessler, M., and Palmer, A. (2020) *State of the research: An annotated bibliography on existing, emerging, and needed research on food policy groups* (2nd edition). Baltimore, MD: Johns Hopkins Center for a Livable Future.
- Sibbing, L.V. and Candel, J.J. (2021) Realizing urban food policy: a discursive institutionalist analysis of Ede municipality, *Food Security* 13(3): 571–582.
- Tohme Tawk, S., Moussa, Z. and Hamadeh, K. S. (n.d.). *Mainstreaming urban agriculture in the Middle East and North Africa: a multi-stakeholder approach*. Conference paper, The 11th European IFSA Symposium, 1-4 April 2014, Berlin, Germany.
- Vara-Sánchez, I., Gallar-Hernández, D., García-García, L., Morán Alonso, N. and Moragues-Faus, A. (2021) The co-production of urban food policies: Exploring the emergence of new governance spaces in three Spanish cities, *Food Policy* (103). 10.1016/j.foodpol.2021.102120.

Wood, B., Barbour, L. and Lindberg, R. (2018) *The Human Right to Food and Water in Australia. A compilation of specific food security strategies*. Melbourne: Right to Food Coalition –Victorian Chapter.

www.foodcllic.eu

PARTNERS

CONTACT US:

Dr. Ferne Edwards, f.edwards@surrey.ac.uk

www.foodclik.eu

#foodclik

Funded
by the European Union